

Importance of Non Surgical Therapy In Periodontology Prior to Surgical Therapy : A Review

Received on : 19-10-2024 | Accepted on : 05-12-2024 | Published on : 10-03-2025

Pooja Bhardwaj

Associate Professor
Department of Periodontology
Rishiraj College of Dental Sciences &
Research Centre
Bhopal, (M.P.)

Abstract

Plaque and calculus are the sole etiological factor for the causation of gingivitis which if not controlled through proper treatment plan can lead to the periodontitis. Thenon surgical therapyforms the base for the further stages of treatment plan in both the gingivitis and periodontitis as this non surgical therapy gives a true idea about whether the patient is indicated for the surgical therapy or not, to what extent the patient is concern about his or her oral health. Taking these considerations, this short communication highlights the importance of non-surgical therapy in controlling the gingival inflammation and then the true decision about the surgical considerations.

Keywords : Plaque, calculus, inflammation, scaling, root planning, attitude, diagnosis

Introduction

In the field of Periodontology, taking into consideration, about the diseased part, so because of inflammation, two diseases are of an utmost important concern; gingivitis and periodontitis. These inflammatory disease has two major important factors; plaque and the calculus. For controlling the inflammation and its progression, the most important thing that needs to be done is the complete elimination of the plaque and the calculus so that the gingival tissues and henceforth the periodontal tissues remain in their healthy state.¹

Non Surgical Therapy In Periodontics

Since it's a proven fact, that the sole etiological factor for the causation of gingivitis and periodontitis is the plaque and the calculus, hence the control of these factors form the basis of non surgical therapy or phase 1 therapy in the field of Periodontology.

A. Measures In Non Surgical Therapy

Non surgical therapy consist of those important measures that are essential to maintain the gingival and the periodontal tissues in their state of equilibrium. It involves the following measures.

1. Scaling and root planning: Once the plaque get mineralized into calculus, then it becomes difficult by the patient itself to remove these deposits from his or her gingiva by routine oral hygiene meas-

ures. Hence a professional cleaning of the teeth is needed to remove these deposits from the gingiva. Henceforth scaling refers to the mechanical removal of plaque and calculus from the gingival surface both supragingivally and subgingivally.² When the tooth and the gingival surface get occupied by these microbial deposits then this microbial colony also makes the cementum of the root surface diseased.⁶ Hence here comes the importance of root planning which refers to the gentle removal of this toxic and necrotic cementum; so that a healthy cemenentum occupies the root surface of the tooth. Hence this scaling and root planning forms the most important measure of all the other oral hygiene measures for making the gingiva in a diseased free state.⁹

It is also a proven fact that if a non surgical intervention i.e. scaling and root planning is carried out, then its maintainance is also an important concern as apart from the periodontist who plays the role in the correct way of scaling and root planning, the major role in the maintainance of this cleaning is by the patient.³ Hence from the patient point of

Access this article online
Website : www.updent.in

Quick Response Code

How to Cite This Article : Bhardwaj et al. - Importance of Non Surgical Therapy In Periodontology Prior to Surgical Therapy : A Review, AJOADUD 2025

view, the following non surgical oral hygiene measures after scaling and root planning are important and they are as follows:⁴

1. Proper brushing technique: In order for the plaque to not get deposited on the tooth surface; proper brushing by the patient is important. This proper brushing technique includes:

a. Method of brushing: In the field of Periodontics, three types of brushing techniques are important: Modified Bass Method, Modified stillman method, Charters method. Now among these methods of toothbrushing, which one needs to be advised to the patient is based upon the clinical condition of the patient and so is instructed by the Periodontist to the patient, that which brushing method is best suitable for the patient so that his or her oral health remains stable.⁴

b. Duration of brushing : it refers to as for how much time the patient brushes his or her teeth as well how many times the patient do toothbrushing. Usually it is advisable that 2 minute brushing time is sufficient to remove deposits from the tooth surface and toothbrushing two times a day is much sufficient to maintain the oral health in a good state.⁴

2. Use of Mouthwashes : The mechanical method particularly after the professional cleaning is not alone sufficient and hence chemical method of plaque control is also important in removal of the plaque and calculus build up from the teeth as well to deal up with the halitosis which is also one of the symptoms of the poor oral health. The prescription of these mouthwashes by the periodontist to the patient depends upon what the patient chief complaint was as a common mouthwash never ever solves all the oral problems of the patients and these prescriptions of the mouthwashes vary from patient to patient as well within the same patient.⁴

3. Use of interdental aids : The biggest disadvantage of the toothbrushing and the mouthwash is that these cannot clean the interdental area in a much effective manner because of which the interdental area is the first site in which the plaque gets accumulated and leads to the initiation of gingivitis. Hence here the role of interdental aids comes into consideration. Interdental aids refer to a manual cleaning device that can remove remnants of food particles from an interdental area and hence helps to maintains the interdental hygiene and the overall oral hygiene in a good manner.⁴

These interdental aids consist of dental floss and the interdental brushes (which are again of two types: narrow space interdental brush; and the wide space interdental brush. Again, which interdental aids is best suitable to the patient is decided by the periodontist based upon the initial clinical condition of the patient.¹⁰

B. Importance of non surgical therapy

Non surgical therapy is carried out for the removal of the plaque and the calculus and by the removal of this plaque and calculus; following important considerations can be seen:

1. Resolution of inflammation : Since this microbial colony leads to the inflammation of the gingiva, hence by the removal of this microbial colony, resolution of the inflammation occurs which gives the clear view about the surgical considerations for a particular clinical case. And if the surgery becomes indicated then it provides the firm base for the better incision and intraoperatively gives proper visibility and accessibility to the operating side.⁷

2. Change of Diagnosis : A properly performed non surgical therapy, gives a more confirmatory view about the provisional diagnosis i.e. whether the provisional diagnosis is same as the final diagnosis (made after non surgical therapy) or the final diagnosis becomes different for that particular clinical case.⁷

3. Patient attitude towards oral health : Non surgical therapy reveals the true attitude of the patients about how much the patient is concerned regarding their oral health and this judgement is done by the periodontist based upon following the proper oral hygiene measures provided to the patient after the professional cleaning. This judgement also shows that these patients are an absolute indication or contraindication to the surgical intervention if needed.⁸

3. Patient attitude towards oral health : Non surgical therapy reveals the true attitude of the patients about how much the patient is concerned regarding their oral health and this judgement is done by the periodontist based upon following the proper oral hygiene measures provided to the patient after the professional cleaning. This judgement also shows that these patients are an absolute indication or contraindication to the surgical intervention if needed.⁸

Image based discussion of the clinical case:

In the first picture a highly inflamed and the swollen gingiva is seen of the left mandibular canine and based upon this clinical presentation, a provisional diagnosis of chronic localized periodontitis was made with respect to the left mandibular canine. Hence the non surgical therapy was started with the scaling, root planning and curettage and the reinforcement of all the oral hygiene measures as described above to the patient and the patient was recalled after 7 days.

In the second picture as the patient came for the follow up after 7 days, complete resolution of the inflammation was noted. Hence the final diagnosis was made as chronic localized gingivitis with respect to the left mandibular canine as compared to the provisional diagnosis which was chronic localized periodontitis as well the need for surgery was eliminated as compared to when the surgical intervention was advised to the patient based upon the provisional diagnosis.

Fig 1 : Highly inflamed swollen gingiva of left mandibular canine.

The Provisional diagnosis was chronic localized Periodontitis

Fig 2 : Complete resolution of the gingival inflammation of Mandibular left canine following the incorporation of non Surgical therapy with the change of final diagnosis to Chronic localized gingivitis.

Conclusion

Non surgical therapy is an important diagnostic factor that can determine the prognosis, treatment plan, and the attitude of the patients towards their oral health. Non surgical therapy should not be skipped at any cost because many of the times it gives a clear clue and the view about managing the proper treatment for the patient and if done in a correct way can result in reverting back the normal gingiva characteristic features from the diseased gingiva.

References

1. Bhansali RS. Non Surgical Periodontal therapy: An update on current evidence. *World J Stomatol* 2014; 3:38-51
2. Of fenbacher S. Periodontal diseases pathogenesis. *Ann Periodontol* 1996;1:821-878.
3. Tanwar J,Dodani K. Non surgical periodontal therapy: A review. *J Oral Res* 2016;8:39
4. Khan S,Khalid T. Non-surgical periodontal therapy effectively improves patient reported outcomes: a systematic review. *Int J Dent Hyg.* 2021;19:18-28.
5. Kloostra PW, Eber RM. Surgical versus non-surgical periodontal treatment: psychosocial factors and treatment outcomes. *J Periodont.* 2006;77:1 253-1 260.
6. Aleo JJ, Farber PA. The presence and biologic activity of cementum bound endotoxin. *J Periodontal.* 1974; 45(9): 672-675.
7. Philstrom BL. A randomized four year study of periodontal therapy. *JPeriodontol.*1981; 52(5):227-242
8. Morrison EC, Hill RW. Short term effects of initial, non surgical periodontal treatment (hygienic phase). *J Clin Periodontol.*1980;7(3):199-211.
9. Ramjford SP. Root planning and curettage. *Int Dent J.* 1980;30(2):93-100.
10. Sweeney PL, Smith BA. Scaling and root planning with and without Periodontal flap surgery. *J Clin Periodontol.* 1986;13(3):205-210.